

Threat Appeals in Road Safety TV Advertisements and their Impact on Youth: An Experimental Study ¹

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Hebatalla EL Semary, Ph.D. - Faculty of Mass Communication Cairo University⁽²⁾Mai AL Khaja ,
PhD-Mass Communication Department, UAEU

Abstract:

Due to long-standing reliance upon negative, fear-based appeals in road safety advertising, this study attempts to examine the effectiveness of threat appeals in persuading Emirati road users to change their attitudes and behaviour in the short and long run. To measure the effectiveness of the threat advertising message, a quasi-experiment was designed, including two groups of Emirati students. Each group is composed of 100 Emirati students selected from two universities. Students were asked to complete a questionnaire at varying time intervals, as the persuasive effects of an advertising message may vary over time. On the other hand, 6 focus groups were constituted. Seven issues related to the impact of road safety ads on young Emiratis were raised and discussed and students proposed a number of suggestions that could help in making road safety awareness more efficient. The findings showed that road safety ads based on threat appeals have positive effects in the short term, but these effects diminish over time. Evidence suggests that threat appeals may influence females rather than males, despite the fact that many of these messages intend to target male road users

Keywords: Threat appeals- Road Safety Advertisements- Emirati Youth-Quasi-experiment

1. Introduction:

Broadly speaking, traffic safety aims to embrace all plans, programmes and traffic regulations and preventive measures to curb or prevent road accidents. Moreover, it seeks to ensure the safety of people and their properties and to preserve the security of the country as well as its human and economic assets.

World Health Organization (WHO) indicates that the rates of deaths caused by traffic accidents in developing countries are high compared to those in developed ones. It is expected that by 2030 traffic accidents will be the third cause of death worldwide in general and in developing countries in particular (1)

In the UAE, statistics by the Ministry of Interior indicate that 52.9% of the perpetrators of the accidents and those injured are in the youth category (18-35 years) and this percentage is increasing due to over-speeding and reckless driving. The statistics also show that out of a total of 963 deaths in the UAE in 2010, 387 youths died in traffic accidents, accounting for 40% of the total deaths of traffic accidents (2)

If the elements of traffic safety are the vehicle, the driver and the pedestrians, the driver is the most important of those elements because he/she protects the vehicle and the pedestrians. This emphasises the importance of driver awareness and ensuring their ability to comprehend and apply the traffic safety measures in order to achieve them in their broad and scientific framework.

Statistics by The General Directorate of Traffic also indicate that the lack of sufficient public awareness of traffic safety measures is the main reason behind many accidents (3). Therefore, it is important to raise public awareness - targeting the youth, in particular - about the need to apply traffic safety measures in order to preserve their lives and the lives of others.

Among all forms of advertising, Al Rashidi (2009) found in his study on the effectiveness of the traffic awareness campaigns that traffic awareness through television affects the behaviour of the driver by highlighting the negative consequences of traffic accidents, whereas the least effective means in the field of

¹ Funded by Roadway, Transportation, and Traffic Safety Research Center, United Arab Emirates University, UAE

traffic awareness were radio and mosques (4). Television advertising aims to persuade road users to adopt safer attitudes and behaviours in order to reduce transport-related injury and mortality. To achieve this goal, road safety advertising uses different persuasion appeals, one of which is a threat or fear.

Witte (2000) defines fear as “a negatively valenced emotion, accompanied by a high level of arousal.” (5) and Willam (2012) believes that fear appeals rely on a threat to an individual’s well-being that motivates him or her toward action (6). Some prefer threat or emotional appeals (legal sanctions (fines, license loss), physical inquiry, or death, social ostracism, or guilt or remorse as a result of causing injury or death to another party), as they have a quick impact and they influence masses of various groups and educational levels, whereas logical appeals require a relatively higher level of education and cultural awareness for the traffic message to achieve its goals.

A study (2000) analysed the content of 189 department of Defence radio PSAs and found that 68% of the military radio PSAs use fear appeals when attempting to persuade listeners to adopt new health and safety practices. (7).

On the other hand, Willams (2012) reviewed the fear appeal literature and concluded that more effective fear appeals result from higher fear arousal, followed by consequences and recommendations to reduce the negativity(8). Similarly, Witte and Allen (2000) analysed more than 100 fear appeal articles. The findings show serious fear (emphasis on the degree of seriousness of the threat and the extent the recipient is exposed to it) to be more convincing than weak fear factors (9).

A third group focused on the effectiveness of the fear message. Tannenbaum & others (2015) found a positive effect of fear appeals on attitudes, intentions and behaviors and the effectiveness was higher among females. The study found no identified circumstances under which they lead to undesirable outcomes(10).

Sarrina Li adopted a quasi-experimental design to examine the relationships between the use of fear appeals and college students’ attitudes and behavioral intentions toward global warming. The study suggested that effective messages in high threat conditions should include both threat and efficacy information(11).

Peters, Ruiter & Koks (2018) conducted qualitative interviews with 33 intervention developers, policymakers, politicians, scientists, and advertising professionals in the Netherlands. The study found that participants involved with the actual intervention development, unlike other participants, were generally convinced that threatening information was to be prevented, but they had to deal with supervisors or funders who prefer threatening communication(12).

As research confirms the effectiveness of threat appeal messages, A'alem (2003) advocates the use of fear or threat appeals in traffic safety advertisements, as he considers the threat appeal as a strong emotion that causes confusion or a sense of guilt or shame (13). This emotion makes the individual more interested in experiencing the behaviours required to reduce the severity and impact of such heightened emotional state.

In the 1970s, fear appeal theories started favouring cognitive perspectives, unlike earlier theories that focused on learning theories perspectives. Recent years marked a return to focus on emotion as an incentive in behaviour change theories (14).

Witte (1992, 1994) developed an extended parallel and illustrated process model. This model proposes that individuals who are confronted with a threatening message will respond either by working to reduce the perceived risk in doing something about the threat (reaction related to control hazard), or they will reduce their perspectives and expectations about the risk through blocking the message (a reaction related to controlling fear) (15).

Lewis, Watsen & White (2010) recommends using fear tactics with great caution, noting the need to adhere to the following three steps:

1. Attracting the individual and keeping him/her alert.

2. We are providing effective recommendations (safe behaviour) to conform with the threat.
3. Increasing the confidence levels of the receiver in his/her ability to perform the recommended behaviour successfully and easily (16).

Excessive use of threat appeals must be cautioned against in TV advertisements watched by the entire family, including children.

On the other hand, the study conducted by Obaid bin Said Al Shaksy from Qaboos University emphasises the significance of rational appeals in the awareness message to emphasise the gravity of the situation and the importance of taking into account the safety aspects when using the road. The study believes that the media can enhance this aspect by dealing with the road user as an active participant in this effort, rather than being accused of it. The study confirms the importance of psychological and social factors that should be taken into account when preparing the media message (17).

Foreign and Arab studies have focused on investigating the role of the media in educating the community on the importance of traffic safety. This includes the study carried out by Mohammad Mehri in the Sultanate of Oman, who assessed traffic awareness programmes, and the means of their delivery. Mehri concluded that what is needed is not only traffic awareness in the media, but a new culture of safe driving by all (18).

Another Gulf study by Al Darie (2009) emphasises that awareness is linked to safety and ignorance is linked to mistake, which refers to the importance of ongoing education and diversification of the means of awareness according to the target segments (19). Here, the role of the media is amplified in developing a vision of a comprehensive media campaign accompanied by the measures and procedures prescribed by officials in the traffic departments.

Based on the discussion above, it becomes clear that earlier studies focused on the analysis of the content of the road safety media message and the effectiveness of these messages on the public recipient in the short run. But the long term effects of threat messages have not received sufficient attention from these studies. This is where the significance of this study lies as it seeks to identify the short and long-term effects of the TV road safety advertising, especially those employing threat appeals on the knowledge, attitudes and behaviours of a sample of Emirati youths. The sample was selected to represent the category most prone to accidents and most affected by them.

2. Goals of the Study:

This study aims to:

1. identify the impact of threat appeals in traffic safety commercials on the public;
2. compare the short and long-term effects of traffic safety commercials;
3. identify the impact of traffic safety commercials on knowledge, trends and behaviour;
4. identify the intermediate factors that limit the impact of traffic awareness commercials on the public; and
5. identify a framework that determines the success of the traffic safety commercials on the public, both in the short and long-term.

The Theoretical Framework of the Study

The theoretical framework of this study is based on Bandura's social learning theory-social cognition theory, which emphasises the importance of observation and imitation of the behaviour of the models seen by the individual through media.

The theory assumes that man is a social being influenced by the trends, feelings, actions and behaviour of others watched through any media, that means, man can learn from others' behavioural models through observation and imitation. Learning by observation refers to the possibility of being indirectly influenced by reward and punishment (20).

3.Hypotheses

1. There are significant differences between the knowledge, attitudes and behaviour of young people who viewed threat road safety ads, logical awareness ads and those who didn't watch any ads.
2. Youth who are exposed to threat-appeal traffic awareness ads are more likely to gain knowledge in the short term and lose knowledge in the long term.
3. Youth who are exposed to threat-appeal traffic awareness ads are more likely to become positive in the short term and less positive in the long term.
4. The more traffic awareness ads rely on threat appeals, the more they influence behaviour in the short term and less in the long term.
5. There are significant differences between gender, age, social environment, education level, and the Emirate to which the respondent belongs and the way the youth are affected by the positive behaviours of fear-appeal traffic awareness ads.
6. The more traffic awareness ads contain reward and punishment content, the higher the positive influence on youths.
7. Young people are more likely influenced by traffic awareness ads if the models presented in the ads are of the same type and age.

4. Methodology

This quasi-experimental study seeks to identify the short and long-term effects of television traffic safety advertisements that rely on threat appeals. It targets a sample of Emirati youths. Three groups have been selected; each one comprises 100 participants of youth (18-35 years). The first group is the control group (formed of students from the University of the UAE and Sharjah), while the other two represent the experiment groups (the first experimental group, which was exposed to threat commercials, is formed of students from the UAE University and the second group which was exposed to logical awareness commercials has been selected from the students of the University of Sharjah). The resemblance of characteristics was taken into account in the process of sampling the participants in each group as much as possible.

To ensure that participants were not pre-exposed to the commercials, both researchers prepared and implemented (six) awareness commercials, three of which were based on threat appeals while the other three were based on logical and rational appeal. The threat appeals commercials were shown to the experimental group of the University of Emirates while the logical appeals commercials were shown to the experimental group of the University of Sharjah.

In addition to that, a survey was designed and conducted with the three groups five times: (1) before and (2) after viewing the commercials, (3) after a month, (4) six months later and (5) a year after the first viewing of the commercials. The survey measured the impact of TV traffic safety commercials on the knowledge,

attitudes and behaviours of Emiratis youth. In order to obtain deep understanding, both researchers used (6) focus groups, each consists of 12 participants, represents a group of youth of a particular age range and includes both males and females.

Three metrics were prepared to measure the impact of traffic awareness on the knowledge, trends and behaviours in the following manner:

Knowledge Scale: The scale consists of 30 points distributed as follows:

Deep knowledge (from 24-30)

Medium knowledge (15-24)

Surface knowledge (1-14)

Attitudes scale: The scale consists of 30 points distributed as follows:

Positive attitude (from 20-30)

Negative attitude (from 10-20)

Unclear (0- less than 10)

Behavioural scale: The scale consists of 20 points distributed as follows:

Positive behaviour (10-20)

Negative behaviour (less than 10)

The Time Frame of the Study

The study was conducted over three years in which the PSAs were prepared and the pilot study was designed during the first year (2013). The experiment was first applied in 2015 on the experimental and control groups in five stages: before and directly after viewing, a month later, after six months and a year after the first viewing.

Findings

1. Characteristics of the experimental and control groups:

Similarities in the characteristics of the experimental and control groups were taken into consideration, as evidenced by the following:

1. Male to female percentages were close across all the groups: 51.9% male and 48.1% female.
2. Participants' ages in each group were as follows: less than 20 years: 13.3%; 20-22 years: 29.6%; 22-24 years: 23%; 24-26 years: 12.6%; 26-28 years: 10.4%; and over 28 years: 11.1%.
3. Emirati citizenship was noticeably greater in each group (63.7%) compared to other nationalities of 36.3%. This is consistent with the proportion of various nationalities within the University of Sharjah and the University of UAE.
4. The diversity of disciplines amongst the participants was noticeable with the literary and the scientific discipline. However, the highest percentage of participants came from the Faculty of Humanities (30.1%), the Economics (11.9%), Sciences and Engineering (10.4%) and then the

College of Law, Food and Agriculture (9.7%), and finally The Information Technology, Medicine and Medical Science (8.9%).

5. 58.5% drive cars while the remaining 41.5% do not drive.
6. 35% of participants in each group have less than five years of driving experience, 24% have less than one year of driving experience and 22.8% are those who have less than ten years of driving experience, while 17.8% have more than ten years of driving experience.
7. 68.4% of participants in each group received driving fines, while the other 31.6% did not.
8. When the participants were asked about their fine history, their responses showed a variety of histories. The majority of fines (50%) were due to exceeding the speed limit, 18.9% due to not using the seat belt, 12.2% due to using mobile phones while driving, 9.5% due to ignoring traffic lights, 4.1% due to not giving priority to pedestrians, 2.7% due to using tinted car windows, and finally 1.3% due to parking on the pedestrians' walkway and to not turning on the headlights. This result reflects the reality of the Emirati life and especially the Emirati youth traffic culture and their modern lifestyle.

2. General Findings:

1. The results of the study reveal a strong relationship between youth and the new media where more than half of the sample (54.8%) are exposed to the new media on a daily basis especially social media ((34.8%) of the youth participants are exposed to social media, 11.1% read electronic newspapers, 8.9% are exposed to mobile commercials on a daily basis). Television comes in the second place with 23.4% and next comes the radio with 15.6%. One of the unexpected results in this study is that participants preferred electronic newspapers to printed newspapers, which comes in the last place amongst the means the youth are exposed to and the percentage of those exposed to them does not exceed 9.6%.
2. This study shows that a reasonable percentage of youth (about 40%) are exposed to TV commercials on a daily basis. There is, in contrast, a considerable percentage who are exposed to TV commercials by chance (26%), which refers to the inability of TV commercials to attract the attention of some youth, or perhaps advertising at times those youth do not normally watch TV. The study shows that youth are exposed to TV commercials primarily in the evenings while many TV awareness commercials are broadcast in the mornings and afternoons which are called dead periods.
3. 80% of the participants in this study watch traffic safety commercials and this turned out to be the most awareness-raising commercials watched, whereas 20% of the participants did not watch that before. This underlines the importance of the production of awareness commercials, the content of this experimental study to ensure no prior exposure to them.
4. Traffic safety commercials viewed by the majority of youths focus on exceeding the speed limit (37%), using mobile phones (36.3%) and seat belts (31.1%). Other important issues, such as the use of car seats for children (9.6%), not crossing the white line (3.7%) and using the right side of the road (3%) received less attention from those responsible for producing the commercials. This raises the question of the reasons behind the focus on specific issues rather than others. Is that the result of scientific studies that confirmed the need for raising awareness of these issues or are they the initiatives and individual decisions by those responsible for producing those commercials?
5. Based on the answers of the participants in the three groups, traffic safety commercials focus on direct templates of direct awareness methods, guide texts shown on screen and hosting traffic experts. More than half of the commercials watched by the participants relied on those direct templates (54.8), while indirect templates such as drama templates (34.6%) and song videos (10.6%)

received less attention. Previous studies have confirmed the ability of indirect templates to influence the public's behaviour more than the direct ones, especially among the youth (21).

6. The participants stressed the dominance of threat appeals and methods (40%) in traffic safety commercials over logical appeals (38.5%). This explains the importance of recognising the impact of these threat appeals and their effectiveness in achieving the goal of traffic safety commercials, which is changing the behaviours of the public. One of the interesting findings in this study is that more than one-third of the participants answered with "I do not know." This result shows that the public does not pay attention to the traffic safety awareness message. This may be due to many reasons, including, for example, relying on advertising direct templates that are not favoured by the youth. The previous results indicate that the youth watch traffic safety commercials, but mostly by chance. So, they do not focus on the awareness message presented, perhaps because of relying on direct templates that are not favoured by the youth. This stresses the importance of paying more attention to the production of the traffic message to achieve its intended outcomes.
7. Participants believe that social media is the most appropriate means to provide traffic safety commercials 44.4%, followed by mobile phones 31.8%, TV 22.2%, then the rest of the traditional means such as the radio and electronic newspapers 11.1% each, after that printed newspapers 5.9%, and finally cinema and lectures about traffic safety 0.74%. This finding conflicts with findings in other studies that confirmed the effectiveness of television in broadcasting the traffic message to the target audience (18).
8. Most of the youths' attitudes toward traffic safety advertisements are negative.
9. The study also revealed that some of the inappropriate elements in the traffic safety advertisements, from participants' point of view, were: the information provided (68.9%), the number (56.3%), the frequency (51.1%), the broadcasting time (65.2%), broadcasting time and duration (67.4%), as well as the means (65.9%), the templates used (61.5%) and in terms of the use of children in them (65.2%).
10. Participants did not believe that the use of threat appeals in traffic safety advertisements was suitable by 55.6%. The study indicates that exaggerating the threat and intimidation might provoke a challenge for the youth, or make them avoid the messages of the advertisements that refer to this threat and intimidation. Thus, the results indicate the need for the systematic, rational and deliberate use of threat appeals, as well as the necessity of using a variety of appeals to include both logical and threat appeals.
11. On the other hand, the study revealed that participants have a positive attitude towards associating the traffic safety advertisements with specific seasons rather than showing them throughout the year by 57.8%. This result suggests that the participants do not care about these types of advertisements and are not convinced by their usefulness.
12. The study revealed that the information aspect of the traffic safety advertisements was very poor as only 39.3% of the participants benefited from the information provided by the TV traffic safety advertisements.
13. The ability of threat appeals to convince the participants to change their traffic behaviour (20.7%) is greater than the logical appeals (3.19%) but it is noticed that the percentage of those convinced to change their behaviour, either through emotional threat appeals or logical, rational appeals is considerably weak, which necessitates greater attention to be paid to producing the traffic message.
14. Traffic safety advertisements only convinced 18.5% of the participants to consider changing their attitudes towards traffic safety issues. This is an extremely small percentage. Interestingly, 2.2% indicated that traffic safety advertisements changed their attitudes towards traffic safety instructions,

but did not succeed in changing their behaviours. This result requires paying more attention to the production of the media traffic message.

15. The study also showed a significant result, and in spite of its small percentage, it is worth considering; 5.9% of the participants believe that the traffic safety advertisements did not achieve any benefit.
16. The reasons why those participants did not benefit from the traffic safety advertisements are because they were shown seasonally (34.1%). Another reason is their reliance on the threat of the consequences of failure to follow traffic safety measures, and direct indicative style (23.7% each). In addition, some (22.2%) emphasised they did not relate to these advertisements as they are reproduced from Western media and so do not reflect the essence of the UAE culture. This finding urges those responsible for traffic safety to consider the need to search for all the components and elements, form and content, in order to make the traffic safety advertisements appropriate for the spirit and environment of the UAE. In this way, the target audience relates to these advertisements.

Hypotheses Testing:

1. First hypothesis: The more youths are exposed to fear-appeal traffic awareness commercials, the more their short-term knowledge is increased while their long-term knowledge is decreased.

The findings of the study showed that 66% of those who were exposed to intimidating traffic awareness advertisements have become more informed about traffic safety—level medium to high, which is quite reasonable, especially if we consider the fact that fear-appeal advertisements do not contain substantial information. However, this rate has dropped to 58% after one month, then went down to 42% after 6 months, and further declined to 31% after one year.

On the other hand, the knowledge of 50% of those who were exposed to logical awareness advertisements has grown to medium/high, and this rate has risen over time to reach 69% after one year.

The above findings indicate that the effect of fear-appeal advertisements was significant after viewing but had declined over time, unlike logical awareness advertisements, which resulted in a sustained increase in youths' knowledge over time. Measuring the differences in knowledge rates between those who were exposed to fear-appeal advertisements and those who were exposed to logical awareness advertisements, substantial differences between them have been identified ($T= 5.122$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$). Hence, we can accept the first hypothesis of this study.

2. Second hypothesis: The more youths are exposed to fear-appeal traffic awareness advertisements, the more their attitudes will become positive in the short term and less positive in the long term.

With regard to the independent variant effect on youths' attitudes, the findings of the study suggest the following.

- The experiment has shown that 65% of respondents' attitudes have turned positive towards traffic safety procedures after viewing the fear-appeal advertisements. However, this rate has dropped down to 34% over time. Measuring the differences in respondents' positive attitudes after one and six months, substantial differences in respondents' knowledge have been identified, showing a downtrend after one year ($T= 4.872$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$).
- Regarding the second group, it has been shown that only 46% of respondents' attitudes turned positive after viewing the logical awareness advertisements. However, this rate has increased steadily over time, reaching 85% after one year. Measuring the differences in respondents' attitudes along the

study period, substantial changes in respondents' attitudes have been identified throughout the study period ($T= 4.233$, $p\text{-value}= .000$, $df=28$)

- Substantial variations have also been identified between the respondents' positive attitudes who were exposed to fear-appeal advertisements and those who were exposed to logical awareness advertisements right after viewing. Hence, we shall accept the second hypothesis.
3. Third hypothesis: The more traffic awareness advertisements rely on threat appeals, the more they influence behaviour in the short term and the less they do in the long term.

The study has shown that 59% of respondents adopted positive behaviours after viewing the fear-appeal advertisements, but this rate has dropped to 25% after one year. Among the common behaviours that respondents adopted after viewing the advertisements were regular checking of the vehicle before driving, showing respect to traffic rules, and refraining from using mobile phones while driving. It should be mentioned that we did not follow the actual change in respondents' attitudes after playing the advertisement but relied only on the poll results that were applied to the respondents five times in which they stated that their behaviours had changed. Measuring the differences between those who adopted positive behaviours after viewing the advertisement over the study period, T-test confirmed substantial changes ($T=5.291$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$), with a downtrend taking place over time. Unlike the previous finding, only 29% of respondents who were exposed to logical awareness advertisements adopted positive behaviours after viewing the advertisement. However, this rate had increased steadily over the course of the study, reaching 71% after one year.

Measuring the variation rate of adopting positive behaviours after viewing, between those who viewed fear-appeal advertisements and those who viewed logical advertisements, substantial differences have been identified ($T= 4.832$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$). Therefore, we can accept the third hypothesis of the study.

4. There are substantial differences in gender, age, economic background, education and emirate in which the respondents live in addition to driving experience and the positive impact of fear-appeal traffic awareness advertisements on youths.

The study findings have shown logical and fear-appeal advertisements to have influenced youths in terms of knowledge, attitudes and behaviours, whereas the knowledge, attitudes and behaviours of the control group remained unchanged.

As far as the two experimental groups are concerned, differences in knowledge, attitudes and behaviours have been identified based on gender, age and driving practice. The findings did not confirm any substantial differences based on respondents' emirate and educational background.

The details of the findings are explained below.

As far as knowledge is concerned, 61% of those whose knowledge increased remarkably (medium to deep) after viewing the fear-appeal advertisements and 77% of those whose knowledge increased after viewing the logical advertisements, were female. Examining the differences between male and female respondents of the fear-appeal group, substantial differences have been identified ($T= 6.345$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$). In addition, substantial differences between male and female respondents have been identified among the logical advertisements group. ($T= 5.891$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$)

Female respondents have invariably acquired more knowledge than male respondents as a result of fear-appeal and logical advertisements over the different periods of the study, although that knowledge did decrease over time. This finding indicates that females are better acquirers of knowledge than males.

As far as the age variable is concerned, the study has shown that more than half (58%) of the respondents in the fear-appeal category, whose knowledge ranged between medium to deep, were below

24 years old, and 69% of those whose knowledge has increased (growing medium to deep) after viewing the logical advertisements were below 24 years old as well. On the other hand, the knowledge of the older category (over 24 years) has decreased, whether after viewing fear-appeal or logical advertisements

Examining the differences between the younger category (below 24 years) in both the fear-appeal and the logical groups, substantial differences have been identified ($T= 4.921$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$) between the two groups: the knowledge of younger respondents in the logical advertisements group has surpassed that of the fear-appeal group. The difference between them has a statistical significance. ($T= 4.542$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$)

Having examined the differences between the two categories (below 24 years and above 24 years) in the fear-appeal group, no statistical significance has been identified to those differences ($T=.354$, $p\text{-value}=.05$), possibly due to the fact that knowledge in fear-appeal advertisements is usually limited. As for the logical commercials group, the differences between the older and younger categories have been shown to have a statistical significance ($T=4.227$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$): the younger respondents were more capable of acquiring knowledge than the older ones. This finding confirms the importance of directing logical awareness advertisements towards younger children, as this age group has better abilities to acquire knowledge. This interpretation is confirmed by the fact that younger respondents have invariably surpassed older ones over the course of the study, which testified to their recall abilities being better than older respondents.

The findings did not reveal any significant statistical differences between the variables of educational specialization, emirate and education levels of respondents after viewing the fear-appeal and logical advertisements.

Moreover, the findings indicate that students coming from low and moderate economic backgrounds represent 71% of those whose knowledge has increased remarkably (medium to deep knowledge) after watching the logical advertisements, and they also represent 65% of those whose knowledge has increased remarkably after watching the fear-appeal advertisements.

Examining the differences existing between students coming from a high economic background and those coming from low and moderate economic backgrounds with regards to fear-appeal advertisements, the differences appear to have a statistical significance ($T=5.113$, $p\text{-value}=.001$, $df=28$). Likewise, the differences between students coming from high economic backgrounds and those coming from low and moderate economic backgrounds of the logical commercials group, seem to have a statistical significance ($T=5.111$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$). This finding can be interpreted as follows: the low economic background students were more keen on protecting their safety and that of their vehicles, being unable to afford repair costs or traffic fines.

Furthermore, the study has shown that respondents who practiced driving represented 59% of those who have acquired medium to deep knowledge after watching the fear-appeal advertisements, and 63% of those who have acquired medium to deep knowledge after watching the logical advertisements. The differences between those who practiced driving and those who did not in both groups (fear-appeal and logical advertisements) have a statistical significance ($T=4.866$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$)

As far as attitudes are concerned, female respondents represented 69% of those whose attitudes towards traffic safety turned positive right after watching the fear-appeal advertisements. Female respondents have invariably represented the higher rate of those whose attitudes turned positive over the course of the study, even though the rate has declined to 51% after one year.

As for the logical advertisements group, male respondents have scored higher (56%) among those whose attitudes turned positive. Male respondents have invariably represented the higher rate of those whose

attitudes turned positive over the course of the study. This rate has increased, even though slightly, reaching 60% after one year.

These findings show fear-appeal advertisements to have a stronger effect right after watching, but this effect decreases gradually over time, especially among female respondents who were more influenced by fear-appeal advertisements. Logical advertisements, however, have increasingly influenced attitudes positively over time, especially among male respondents. This testifies to the fact that females are more influenced by emotions whereas males are controlled by their minds when considering a behaviour change. The findings show that the chances of influencing females through traffic safety advertisements are higher than males, a fact to be considered by makers and planners of such advertisements who primarily seem to target males.

Examining the differences between the fear-appeal and logical groups, the differences between females' positive attitudes after watching the fear-appeal and logical advertisements seem to have a statistical significance ($T=4.687$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$), and so do the differences between the positive attitudes of males after watching the fear-appeal and logical advertisements ($T=4.921$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$). This indicates that females are more positively influenced by fear-appeal advertisements, whereas males are more influenced by logical advertisements.

As far as the age variable is concerned, the study has shown that 68% of those whose attitudes have been influenced positively after watching the fear-appeal advertisements were from the younger category. This rate has decreased noticeably over the course of the study, dropping to 49% after one year. This reflects a characteristic of college students who are easily affected but will readily let go.

As for logical advertisements, older youths represented a higher rate (54%) of those whose attitudes turned positive after watching. However, the differences between them and respondents of the younger category do not have a statistical significance.

The study has also shown that students coming from low and moderate economic backgrounds represented 66% of those whose attitudes turned positive after watching the fear-appeal advertisements and 65% of those whose attitudes turned positive after watching the logical advertisements. Substantial differences between the two categories in both the fear-appeal and logical groups have been identified ($T=9.317$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=27$)

As far as the respondents' ability to drive, the study has shown that positive attitudes were higher (52%) among students who could not drive. However, the differences among them were not of a statistical significance, which is an unexpected finding. The study also revealed that respondents who did not have a traffic violation history had more positive attitudes than those who had a history of traffic violations in both the fear-appeal advertisements and logical groups.

As far as the educational specialization variable is concerned, the study has shown non-science college students to constitute the higher rate (51%) of those whose attitudes have turned positive after watching the fear-appeal advertisements. However, the differences between them and science college students were not of a statistical significance. As for the logical advertisements, the rate was the same among science and non-science college students (50% each). This confirms that education specialization is not a variable that influences the respondents' positive attitudes towards traffic safety procedures.

As far as behaviour is concerned, respondents scored very low in terms of behaviour change after watching the fear-appeal and logical advertisements, which makes sense. Therefore, we have examined the differences in behaviour change between male and female respondents over the three periods: 1 month, 6 months, and 1 year. Female respondents constituted 63% of those whose behaviours have changed one month after watching the fear-appeal advertisements, and male respondents represented 55% of those whose behaviours changed one month after watching the logical advertisements.

Having examined the differences between female and male respondents one month after watching the fear-appeal advertisements, the differences appear to be of a statistical significance ($T=.529$, $p\text{-value}=.001$, $df=28$) and so do the logical advertisements. This indicates that females were more behaviourally affected by fear-appeal advertisements and males by logical advertisements.

Female respondents have invariably scored higher than their male counterparts over the study periods with regards to fear-appeal advertisements, whereas male respondents scored higher in the logical advertisements group. We have also noticed an increase in the rates of respondents' behavioural change over the years with regards to logical advertisements and a decrease with regards to fear-appeal advertisements. This indicates that the fear-appeal effect is strong but diminishes over time.

As far as the age variable is concerned, older youths were shown to exhibit the most change in the long term, especially after watching the logical advertisements. Younger youths, on the other hand, were more behaviourally influenced in the short term with regards to the fear-appeal advertisements.

Examining the differences between younger and older youths, substantial differences have been identified among them with regards to the fear-appeal and logical advertisements ($T=8.331$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$)

The study has further shown that students coming from low and moderate economic backgrounds of both the logical and fear-appeal groups were more willing to adopt a positive attitude than higher-income students. Differences between both sets of students have a statistical significance ($T=4.231$, $p\text{-value}=.001$, $df=28$)

As far as the variables of educational specialization and emirate, the findings did not reveal any statistical differences of significance.

Based on all of the above, we accept the hypothesis that there are substantial differences in terms of gender, age, economic background, educational specialization, ability to drive, and the respondents' emirate and the **partial** influence of fear-appeal commercials on youths. Substantial differences have been identified based on the factors of gender, age, economic background and the respondent's ability to drive. No substantial differences have been identified with regard to the variables of educational specialization and respondents' emirate.

5. The more traffic awareness commercials contain reward and punishment content, the stronger their positive influence on youths.

57% Of those who watched the fear-appeal advertisements and changed their attitudes towards traffic safety procedures stated - right after watching- that safety advertisements had focussed on punishment and ignored reward. However, this rate has dropped drastically over the course of the three tests (1 month, 6 months, and 1 year), slumping to 33% after one year.

On the other hand, 41% of those who watched logical advertisements and changed their attitudes towards traffic safety procedures stated that safety advertisements ad focussed on reward rather than punishment. However, this rate has increased over time, reaching 68% after one year.

Applying the T-test to the findings of both groups right after watching the advertisements, substantial differences have been identified between the two groups as ($T=7.112$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$), which indicates that focussing on punishment alone in fear-appeal advertisements results in strong effects in the short term but tends to diminish in the long term. On the other hand, focussing on the reward alone in logical advertisements results in weak, direct effects but tends to increase in the long term.

The above discussion of the findings indicates that the reward and punishment elements are important for the successful delivery of the traffic awareness message, and hence:

- 1. Youths are more likely to be influenced by traffic awareness commercials if they can relate more to the character types presented in those commercials in terms of gender, age group and social background.**

The findings of the study show that 56% of those who watched fear-appeal traffic awareness advertisements and consequently changed their attitude towards traffic safety procedures have actually identified with the character types presented in those advertisements, i.e. the types of characters presented in those advertisements were of the same gender, age group, and social background. Moreover, 59% of those who watched the logical traffic safety advertisements and consequently changed their attitudes towards traffic safety have identified with character types presented in those advertisements in terms of age, gender and social background. The differences between the findings of the two experimental groups have a statistical significance ($T= 4.68$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$) and indicate that using character types similar to the target audience in terms of gender or age in traffic safety advertisements has a positive influence on changing youths' attitudes, whether the appeals used in those commercials were of the “threat” or the “logical” types.

The study has also shown that 60% of those who watched the fear-appeal traffic awareness advertisements and consequently changed their attitudes towards traffic safety procedures have actually done so because they found character types similar to themselves in those advertisements, and 55% of those who watched the logical traffic safety advertisements and consequently changed their attitudes towards traffic safety procedures have done so because they related to character types similar to themselves in terms of age, gender and social background in those advertisements. The differences between the findings of both groups have a statistical significance. $T= -4.832$, $p\text{-value}=.000$, $df=28$

Having said that, we accept the hypothesis that youths are more likely to be influenced by traffic awareness advertisements if they can relate more to the character types presented in those advertisements in terms of gender, age group and social background.

Conclusion

- 1. The study has found that traffic safety advertisements require both threat and logic appeals in order to achieve their desired goals. Threat appeals can achieve its objectives in the short term, whereas logic appeals achieve its objectives in the long term.**
- 2. The study has also shown that the effects of threat appeals can be strong immediately after watching but gradually wear out until they disappear completely, whereas the effects of logic appeals are weak immediately after watching but increase over time to reach very high levels.**
- 3. The preliminary study has shown that 80% of youths watch traffic safety advertisements only irregularly and coincidentally due to the following reasons:**
 - a. Those advertisements are aired during awkward timings (morning and noon), whereas the study has shown youths to be watching TV mostly in the evening.**
 - b. Traffic safety advertisements tend to focus on direct clichés such as on-screen guideline texts and hosting traffic experts (54.8%), a style that does not seem to appeal to youths.**
 - c. Traffic safety advertisements tend to focus on certain topics, such as over-speeding, using a mobile phone while driving and not using seatbelts, and repeat these topics continuously, while ignoring other important topics, such as children’s seating, not running over the “while lines” and sticking to the right side of the road. This causes youths to get bored with those advertisements.**
 - d. Youths believe that TV is not the best medium to present traffic awareness advertisements, preferring social media over it (44.4% of respondents) which they**

consider to be the most appropriate for presenting traffic awareness advertisements, followed by smartphones (31.8%), TV (22.2%), then by other conventional media.

- e. **Most youths have negative attitudes towards traffic safety advertisements, perceiving them to be inappropriate to them, whether in terms of the information presented (68.9%), volume (56.3%), frequency (51.1%), airing time (65.2%), or duration (67.4%); and also in terms of media (65.9%), clichés used (61.5%) and reference to children (65.2%).**
 - f. **The production quality of TV traffic safety advertisements was low, with only 39.3% of respondents reporting to have benefited from the information presented in them. Traffic safety advertisements have also failed to convince more than 18.5% of respondents to consider changing their attitudes towards traffic safety topics. 5.9% Of respondents stated that they hardly benefited from traffic safety advertisements.**
 - g. 22.2% Of respondents said they did not identify with those advertisements because they seem to be copied from Western media and did not reflect the UAE environment.
4. The study has underlined the need to pay attention to women when designing the traffic awareness message, as women were shown to watch traffic awareness advertisements more frequently and are more influenced by them in terms of knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours, particularly with regards to fear-appeal advertisements, even though such advertisements were essentially directed at male audience. This finding can be interpreted in light of the following:
- a) Females frequently watch more than their male counterparts of the youth category, as evidenced in previous studies. Thus the chance of women being exposed to the traffic safety advertisements is higher.
 - b) Women tend to be influenced by both emotions and logic. Therefore their response to fear-appeal advertisements tends to be faster and stronger than that of their men counterparts.
5. Students coming from low and moderate economic backgrounds tend to be more influenced by traffic safety advertisements in terms of knowledge and behaviour than students coming from high economic backgrounds, particularly with regards to fear-appeal advertisements. This may be interpreted in the context of their limited financial means, which forces them to be more conscious about protecting not only their safety but also the safety of their vehicles.
6. The findings have underscored the need to pay attention to the younger youth category when designing traffic safety advertisements, as they tend to exhibit better attention and grasp of information as well as willingness to change behaviour than other categories. This is evidenced in the following findings:
- a) Younger students (undergraduate) were shown to have been more influenced by fear-appeal traffic awareness advertisements than older, post-graduate students. The opposite holds true with regards to logical traffic safety advertisements, with the differences between them having a statistical significance.
 - b) Older youths tend to be the more willing to change their behaviours in the long term, especially after viewing the logical advertisements. Younger youths, on the other hand, are more behaviourally influenced in the short term with regards to the fear-appeal group.

7. The first three hypotheses have been accepted, as the findings have shown that the more youths are exposed to fear-appeal traffic awareness advertisements, the more their knowledge, attitudes and behaviours tend to increase and change in the short term and decrease in the long term.
8. Substantial differences have been identified in terms of gender, age, economic background, and ability to drive, and youths being influenced by fear-appeal traffic awareness advertisements. The differences in terms of the emirate and educational specialization were shown not to have a statistical significance. Hence, this hypothesis has been partially accepted.
9. The hypothesis “the more traffic awareness advertisements contain reward and punishment content, the higher the positive influence on youths” has been accepted based on the findings that fear-appeal advertisements focus on the punishment that has a short-term impact, whereas logical advertisements focus on reward that has long-term effects. This indicates that traffic awareness advertisements require punishment and reward content in order to achieve the desired outcome in the short term and ensure it lasts in the long term.
10. The hypothesis “Youths are more likely to be influenced by traffic awareness advertisements if they can relate more to the character types presented in those advertisements in terms of gender, age group and social background” has been accepted, based on the finding that using character types that resemble the target audience in terms of gender and age in traffic advertisements has a positive influence on changing the attitudes and behaviours of youths, whether the appeals used in those advertisements were of the “threat” or the “logic” types.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Violating traffic safety rules poses a risk to UAE society, which is why the government is keen on minimizing violation incidents. Based on the findings of this study, we recommend the following:

- There is a need to establish a clear media policy regarding traffic safety for all national institutions to adopt and work jointly in order to achieve its objectives.
- Before designing and airing traffic safety advertisements, traffic authorities should consider the need to extensively research the target audience (youths) in terms of lifestyles, their media exposure habits, and their preferred media of communication; they should also research the categories of those involved in traffic accidents, the causes behind that, and the methods that can be more efficient in influencing their behaviours.
- Habits, culture, and the unique characteristics of the UAE society should also be generally considered, as social norms have a huge impact on youths’ behaviours, lifestyles, commuting means and the way they benefit from the mass media.
- The extent to which UAE youths benefit from the mass media should be identified in order to create a media plan that defines the media channels through which youths are to be reached. UAE youths access social media sites, such as Facebook and YouTube, more frequently than they read newspapers or listen to the radio. Therefore, it would be more effective to reach out to them with traffic safety advertisements through these channels (e.g., publishing YouTube videos).
- It is vitally important that the objectives of traffic safety advertisements should be crystal clear in terms of knowledge, attitudes and behaviours, in order to achieve the desired positive effects and, most importantly minimizing the rates and severity of road accidents.
- To achieve this goal, authorities should use different methods and various appeals, rather than restricting themselves to certain tactics and appeals.

- It is essential to raise awareness among youths in the UAE on preventive or safe practices, safety requirements in vehicles, risk factors and potentially dangerous behaviours when driving. This should be done through various appeals, including carefully designed and used threat appeals.
- To change unsafe behaviours of UAE youths and reinforce behaviours based on recognizing the importance of traffic safety, various threats, emotional and logical appeals can be used to appeal to all the different minds of youths and encourage them to adopt scientific thinking.
- It has to be admitted that remedying wrong traffic practices of youths in the UAE cannot be achieved overnight or simply because there are enough reasons for that. All the social and economic aspects surrounding such practices should be uncovered, and traffic safety awareness messages should be sustained, diversified and multiplied. Further, all age groups should be adequately covered, whether directly or indirectly, rather than focussing on males and leaving out females. Such messages should be disseminated around the year rather than be restricted to certain periods.
- The responsibility of those in charge of traffic safety advertisements is huge, which underlines the need to train specialized media professionals on all matters relating to traffic awareness culture, UAE society, youths' lifestyles, and how traffic safety messages are prepared and produced. Media messages that aim to change attitudes and behaviours are never an individual effort but should be prepared, produced and supervised by an integral team of message topics experts and specialists in communication, advertisements, psychology, and sociology, among others.
- It is important to examine feedback throughout all the stages of preparing, planning, and executing traffic safety advertisements, by applying multiple preliminary testing to all the stages of preparing and producing interventions and aired messages and polling for two categories of the target audience, namely those specialized in traffic safety and the target public, through holding special meetings to assess such materials in relation to the target public using the focussed groups style and other similar methods.
- It is vitally important to diversify media inputs so as to suit all the different educational levels of youths. Once the appropriateness of public communication tools has been established, it is mandatory to exert additional efforts in order to use special media inputs designed for the limited-education category by using appropriate methods, such as posters, images, and face-to-face communication rather than restricting oneself to public communication only.
- Commercial media inputs using local celebrities in different artistic and sports fields to convey the messages (with real-life shots of the environment close to the target audience and its society) make messages more dynamic and capable of attracting the audience much more than other commercial media inputs. However, it is mandatory that such inputs should be presented artistically, with a sophisticated form, style and suspense elements of music and other similar content, in addition to the scientific approach and clear presentation. Preparation, performance, music, images, language, during and timing should all be integrated with each other.
- It is also important to consider the timing of airing traffic safety messages in public communication. Timing should be considered during all seasons, social events and other factors affecting the communication habits of the target youths. It is equally important to monitor and follow up on traffic safety messages as per the set schedule, with due attention paid to the frequency of airing each message based on their significance.

References:

- Colin D. Mathers, Dejan Loncar (2005) Updated projections of global mortality and burden of disease, 2002-2030: data sources, methods and results, World Health Organization October 2005 , pp.5-8*

- ii. Ministry of Interior's Directorate Traffic, Road traffic accident Statistical Annual Report 2015, Abu Dhabi, UAE
- iii. Ministry of Interior's Directorate Traffic, Road traffic accident Statistical Annual Report 2010, Abu Dhabi, UAE
- iv. Al Rashidi A.(2009) Assessing the effectiveness of Road awareness campaigns, Nauf University for Traffic Sciences, Research Center, Riyadh,Saudi Arabia, pp.521-569
- v. Witte K. (1992) Putting the fear back into fear appeals: The extended Parallel Process Model, Communication Monographs, Vol.59, pp.329-349
- vi. Williams K. C.(2012) Fear appeal theory, Research in Business & Economics Journal;Mar2012, Vol. 5, p1
- vii. Borg M., Cicotte D., Finks C. & Mercado C. (2000) Using Fear to Reach Military Members: A Content-analytic Study of Defense Department PSAs, University of Oklahoma, December
- viii. Williams, op.cit, pp.7-8
- ix. Witte K. & Allen M.(2000) A Meta-Analysis of Fear Appeals: Implications for Effective Public Health Campaigns, Health Education and Behavior,Vol.27 (5), October ,pp.591-615
- x. Tannenbaum M. B., Hepler J.,Zimmerman R.,Saul and Jacobs, Wilson & Albarracin (2015)Appealing to Fear:A meta analysis of Fear Appeal Effectiveness and Theories, Psychological Bulletin , Vol.4, (6), 1178-1204
- xi. Sarrina Li, Shu-Chu (2014)Fear Appeals and College Students' Attitudes and Behavioral Intentions Toward Global Warming, The Journal of Environmental Education, Vol. 45 (4)
- xii. Peters G., Ruiter R. & Kok G.(2018)Threatening communication: a qualitative study of fear appeal Threatening communication: a qualitative study of fear appeal effectiveness beliefs among intervention developers, policy makers , politicians, scientists and advertising professionals, International Journal of Psychology Vol 49 (2), pp. 71-79 .
- xiii. A'Alam, S.(1999) Studies in Traffic Media in Egypt and GCC, second edition, Dar al Thakafa Al Arabia, p. 74-76
- xiv. Williams, op.cit, 9-11
- xv. Witte K (1994) Fear control and danger control: A test of the extended parallel process model (EPPM). Communications Monographs 61: 113-134
- xvi. Lewis IM, Watson B, White KM (2010) Response efficacy: the key to minimizing rejection and maximizing acceptance of emotion-based anti-speeding messages. Accident Analysis & Prevention 42: 459-467
- xvii. Bener A. & Crundall D. (2005) Road Traffic Accidents in the United Arab Emirates compared to Western countries, Advances in transportation studies an international journal section A6,
- xviii. Hammoudi A., Karani, G., & Littlewood J. (2014) Road traffic Accidents among Drivers in Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates, Journal of Traffic and Logistic Engineering, Vol. 2, No. 1, March
- xix. Ali Humaid Al Darei (2009) evaluation of the effectiveness of speed Cameras on road safety in the Emirate of Abu Dhabi roads, MS Thesis in civil engineering, UAEU, June 2009

xx. *Griffin, E., Ledbetter, A. & Sparks, G.(2014) , A First Look at Communication Theory, 9th edition, McGraw Hill*

xxi. *Rosengren, K. & Windahl S (1989).Media Matter: TV use in childhood and Adolescence , USA, Ablex Publishing Corporation*